

Related thesis: Advancements in ground-based aerosol optical depth measurement and measurement-modelling synergies

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ETH Zurich, 2026

Related chapter: Chapter 6: Aerosol classification challenges and long-term variations in global aerosol optical depth and aerosol types based on Sun and sky photometer observations

6.5 Appendix of Chapter 6

6.5.1 Selection criteria for the reference clusters and classifications

Reference stations

Table 6.4: Stations used to retrieve the reference cluster of each type as they appear in the AERONET website.

Urban/Industrial

ATHENS-NOA, Belsk, Billerica, Brookhaven, CCNY, Columbia_SC, GSFC, Hamburg, Leipzig, Lille, Mainz, MD_Science_Center, Minsk, Moldova, Moscow_MSU_MO, Paris, Stennis, UMBC and Wallops

Biomass burning

Abracos_Hill, Alta_Floresta, Concepcion, Cuiaba, Etosha_Pan, LOS_FIEROS_98, Mongu, Senanga, Skukuza and Zambezi

Dust

Agoufou, Bahrain, Banizoumbou, Blida, Dahkla, Dakar, Djougou, Mezaira, Mussafa, Ouagadougou and Solar_Village

Mixed

Anmyon, BeijingChen-Kung_Univ, Gosan_SNU, Gwangju_GIST, Osaka, Pokhara, Pune, Shirahama, Silpakorn_Univ, Taipei_CWB and XiangHe

Maritime

Lanai, Midway_Island, REUNION_ST_DENIS, Sable_Island and Tahiti

General thresholds

All inversions used for any purpose are valid if they satisfy the following conditions, which are based on related work (Dubovik et al., 2002; Li et al., 2014; Hamill et al., 2016; AERONET documentation cited earlier in the thesis text; thesis Chapter 5) and empirical examination of the data for our study (Section 2.1 for definitions of all properties):

$0.03 < \text{AOD} < 4.5$ at 440 nm, Sky residual $\leq 7\%$, Sun residual < 0.8 , Coincident size distribution and related parameters must be level 2, $-0.03 < \text{EAE}_{440-870} < 3.5$, $0.6 < \text{SSA}_{440} \leq 1$ (minimum 0.7 for all reference clusters), $0.2 < \text{AAE}_{440-870} < 4.5$, $R_{\text{eff}} < 3.5$, $C_{\text{VT}} < 4.5$. Also, all other parameters must be above 0. Finally, AOD difference < 0.025 at 440 nm and < 0.02 for the other wavelengths between coincident direct and almucantar scan.

Reference clusters

To create the reference clusters, we used a set of additional empirical thresholds based on the cited literature (Section 6.1), Chapter 5 and the behaviour of the data. The thresholds for each type and other conditions are below.

Urban/Industrial:

$\text{EAE}_{440-870} > 1.45$, $\text{AOD}_f > 0.03$ and $\text{AOD}_c < 0.06$ at 440 nm, $\text{FMF} > 0.75/0.35$ at 440/870 nm, $\text{SSA}_{440} > 0.93$, $0.5 < \text{AAE}_{440-870} \leq 1.32$, $\text{IRI} < 0.016$, $\text{RRI} < 1.53$ and rejected all data known or suspected as affected by wildfire smoke according to the information mentioned at the end of this subsection.

Biomass burning:

$\text{EAE} > 1.5$, $\text{AOD}_f > 0.03$ at 440 nm, $\text{AOD}_c < 0.06$ at 440 nm, $\text{FMF} > 0.8/0.5$ at 440/870 nm, $0.84 < \text{SSA}_{440} < 0.94$, $\text{AAE}_{440-870} < 1.8$ and only specific months depending on the station: August to October for all South American stations. June to October for Mongu, Senanga and Zambezi. July to October for the rest.

Dust:

$\text{EAE}_{440-870} < 0.7$, $\text{AOD}_f < 0.3/0.1$ at 440/870 nm, $\text{AOD}_c > 0.05$ at 440 nm, $\text{FMF} < 0.5/0.35$ at 440/870 nm, $0.84 < \text{SSA}_{440} < 0.95$, $\text{AAE}_{440-870} > 0.8$ and $\text{IRI} < 0.01$.

Mixed:

$0.4 < \text{EAE}_{440-870} < 1.6$, $\text{AOD}_f > 0.02$ at 440 nm, $\text{AOD}_c > 0.02$ at 440 nm, $0.1 < \text{FMF} < 0.95$ at 440 nm, $0.8 < \text{SSA}_{440} < 0.96$, $\text{AAE}_{440-870} < 1.8$

Maritime:

$0.1 \leq \text{EAE}_{440-870} \leq 1$, $\text{AOD}_f < 0.06/0.04$ at 440/870 nm, $\text{AOD}_c > 0.015$ at 440 nm, $\text{FMF} < 0.45$ at 870 nm, $\text{SSA}_{440} > 0.97$, $0.85 \leq \text{AAE}_{440-870} \leq 1$ and AOD at 440 nm ≤ 0.2

IRI was always 0.0005 for the final cluster of maritime aerosols and MD was not possible to calculate properly. So, we used instead a random gaussian distribution with mean 0.0005, standard deviation 0.0002 and ensured all values of the distribution being above 0 and no more than 0.001.

For the reference clusters of biomass burning, dust and mixed we used only level 2 AERONET data. For urban/industrial we included level 1.5 inversions of SSA, AAE and refractive index that satisfy our conditions. For maritime, we used only level 1.5 for those 4 parameters.

To decide the thresholds of urban/industrial and biomass burning, we used several known wildfire episodes (which we removed from the reference cluster of urban/industrial) to better

assess the differences between the two types. In more details, we identified large scale episodes such as Canadian fires of 2023 (Chapter 5) through literature (Hodzic et al., 2007; Trickl et al., 2015; Brey et al., 2018; Baars et al., 2021; Eck et al., 2023; Masoom et al., 2023; Masoom et al., 2025), Global Wildfire Information System (GWIS) data (<https://gwis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/apps/gwis.statistics/seasonaltrend>), Fire Information for Resource Management System (FIRMS) maps (<https://firms.modaps.eosdis.nasa.gov/map/#d:24hrs;@0.0,0.0,3.0z>) and international media. For Athens, due to the frequent wildfires in the nearby area during the summer, we used additionally data from the Greek fire brigade service (<https://www.fireservice.gr/el/synoladedomemon>) and Greek media articles or videos (including public dissemination from the National Observatory of Athens and World Wildlife Fund or WWF) to identify known smoke episodes and large wildfires nearby. Then we studied the statistics of the aerosol properties of data within the clusters according to a provisional selection of urban/industrial reference cluster, during those events, the warm period and all months without those events. According to the results, we re-adjusted the thresholds and removed all data related to wildfire episodes. A list of the fire events considered is in Table 6.5.

Table 6.5: List of all locations and times with measurements we considered as potentially affected by significant amount of smoke from wildfires.

Region	Year	First month	First day	Last month	Last day	Stations affected
Siberia	2010	7	29	8	16	Moscow, Minsk, Belsk, Kishinev
Eastern Europe	2023	10	1	10	3	Kishinev and Athens
Greece	2008	7	23	8	13	Athens
Greece	2009	8	20	9	4	Athens
Greece	2010	7	17	7	26	Athens
Greece	2010	8	14	8	24	Athens
Greece	2011	8	17	8	25	Athens
Greece	2012	6	16	6	26	Athens
Greece	2012	8	20	9	3	Athens
Greece	2013	8	7	8	10	Athens
Greece	2014	7	10	7	19	Athens
Greece	2015	7	18	7	28	Athens
Greece	2016	6	28	8	3	Athens
Greece	2016	7	29	8	10	Athens
Greece	2017	8	12	8	17	Athens
Greece	2018	7	23	8	3	Athens
Greece	2019	8	13	8	26	Athens

Greece	2020	7	22	7	24	Athens
Greece	2021	8	3	9	3	Athens
USA	2007	5	23	6	23	Stennis
USA	2016	10	23	12	11	East/SouthEast USA
USA	2016	3	22	3	31	Stennis
USA	2020	9	14	9	16	East/SouthEast USA
USA	2022	4	29	8	21	Stennis
USA	2023	9	24	10	1	East/SouthEast USA
USA	2023	6	2	6	16	East/SouthEast USA
USA	2023	6	27	7	1	East/SouthEast USA
USA	2024	7	21	7	24	East/SouthEast USA
Europe	2003	8	1	8	31	West and central Europe
Germany	2017	8	20	8	23	All Germany, Belarus and Poland
Germany	2018	7	1	7	31	Hamburg
Germany	2020	9	10	9	12	Hamburg and Leipzig
Germany	2023	5	23	5	25	Hamburg
Germany	2023	6	9	6	12	Hamburg
France	2023	6	26	6	27	Paris and Lille
France	2023	9	29	10	1	Lille and Paris

After the end of the above procedure, we applied the criterion of $MD < 2$ from the centroid on the remaining data points.

Differences of reference clusters between the periods

Table 6.6: Percentage differences of the centroids and variances between reference clusters calculated only from data until 2012 and data starting from 2013.

Centroid differences %					
Type	ΔEAE	ΔAAE	ΔSSA	ΔRRRI	ΔIRI
Urban/Industrial	-1.61	-1.07	0.11	0.48	-5.57
Biomass Burning	-1.94	4.34	0.84	-0.34	-13.05
Dust	4.50	9.46	0.33	-0.81	-2.97
Mixed	3.58	5.18	0.53	-0.05	-4.22
Maritime	23.99	1.54	0.06	-0.21	-1.21
Variance differences %					
Type	ΔEAE	ΔAAE	ΔSSA	ΔRRRI	ΔIRI
Urban/Industrial	-10.81	4.66	-0.82	8.96	3.09
Biomass Burning	42.23	-9.44	3.03	-2.07	5.66
Dust	4.71	-11.48	7.02	-17.06	2.30
Mixed	0.34	-5.30	11.62	4.15	17.49
Maritime	-5.85	51.50	-7.04	-7.25	19.42

6.5.2 Aerosol classifications methodological details

Here we describe the Mahalanobis distance thresholds which define whether a measurement will correspond to undefined aerosols or to the nearest type. Also, we explain the methodology for the averaging of annual classifications over extended regions (Figure 6.7).

Undefined aerosols

Undefined aerosols are all the measurements satisfying one of the following conditions described below. MD_{\min} is the Mahalanobis distance of the measurement with the nearest cluster and MD_{2nd} with the second nearest cluster:

1. For $MD_{\min} < 7$: $MD_{2nd} - MD_{\min} \leq 0.1$ or $MD_{2nd} - MD_{\min} \leq 3\%$ of MD_{\min} .
2. For $7 \leq MD_{\min} < 8$: $MD_{2nd} - MD_{\min} \leq 0.5$
3. For $8 \leq MD_{\min} < 10$: $MD_{2nd} - MD_{\min} \leq 1$
4. For $10 \leq MD_{\min} < 12$: $MD_{2nd} - MD_{\min} \leq 2$
5. For $12 \leq MD_{\min} < 14$: $MD_{2nd} - MD_{\min} \leq 3$
6. $MD_{\min} > 14$

The selection is based on the cluster-to-cluster Mahalanobis distance and the MD values among the different locations.

Secondary types

Measurements of aerosol properties with their closest cluster being mixed aerosols that do not satisfy the conditions of undefined aerosols are assigned to a secondary type corresponding to the second nearest cluster in they satisfy the conditions below. Otherwise, they remain simply mixed.

If the Mahalanobis distance of a measurement from the 3rd nearest cluster is MD_{3rd} , then the conditions to assign a secondary type are:

1. $MD_{2nd} - MD_{3rd} \geq 0.5$
2. $1 - MD_{2nd} / MD_{3rd} > 0.03$

Regional averages

For Figure 6.7 we calculated for each station the seasonal %AOD share per type for all years. Then the annual mean value of all valid seasons. Finally, the mean of the annual averages of all stations within the region. The same to the AOD, from the same data.

For a season to be valid requires at least 30 measurements per period (1993-2012 and 2013-2024). For a station to be valid must contain:

1. >100 measurements per period
2. >3 different years with measurements per period
3. >2 months with measurements per period
4. >1 valid seasons per period

Monthly climatologies, require at least at 10 measurements per month for the entire period of the climatology. The region separation is according to the coordinates in Table 6.7.

Table 6.7: Coordinates forming the regional separation in Figure 6.7.

Region	Longitude		Latitude		Number of stations
	Minimum	Maximum	Minimum	Maximum	
West USA	-125.00	-108.00	31.00	57.00	2
Central, East USA	-107.00	-52.00	32.50	58.00	13
Mexico, South_USA	-103.00	-88.80	11.70	31.00	2
Carribbean Sea	-83.70	-59.00	13.00	26.30	6
South America	-80.00	-35.00	-28.00	7.00	7
South Atlantic Ocean	-34.00	-5.00	-90.00	0.00	1
South Indian Ocean	50.00	90.00	-90.00	0.00	1
Southern Africa	0.00	45.00	-45.00	5.00	3
Australia	110.00	169.00	-35.00	-5.00	4
South Asia	90.00	124.00	-10.00	22.40	7
East Asia	100.00	150.00	22.50	45.00	15
Siberia	75.00	150.00	45.00	70.00	1
India	64.90	90.00	6.00	40.40	9
Middle East	29.00	58.90	19.70	37.20	8
North Africa	-6.00	19.00	5.80	23.00	4
Central, East Atlantic	-27.00	-7.00	14.00	31.80	6
East Mediterranean	10.50	28.00	35.00	42.30	8
West Mediterranean	-10.00	10.50	35.00	42.30	7
Central, North Europe	-1.00	19.20	42.50	59.00	17
East Europe	20.20	41.00	42.50	59.00	7

6.5.3 Additional comparisons of classifications from 2 and 5 parameters

Here we show the comparisons for all selected stations (including those rejected from the rest of the study) between the classifications using 2 or 5 parameters for the aerosol types omitted in Section 6.2.3.

Figure 6.22: Map of comparison of AOD share percentage attributed to urban/industrial by the method using only 2 parameters (EAE and SSA) and all 5 parameters. The graph shows all selected AERONET stations and a histogram of all differences. The histogram shows mostly small differences, but the few large differences, appear on the map on locations with large cities, industries or largely prone to wildfires. Therefore, several of the differences in the case of biomass burning were related to the exchange of measurements between urban/industrial and biomass burning when changing the number of parameters.

Figure 6.23: Map of comparison of AOD share percentage attributed to urban/industrial by the method using only 2 parameters (EAE and SSA) and all 5 parameters. The graph shows all selected AERONET stations and a histogram of all differences. The histogram shows mostly small differences, but the few larger differences appear close to major deserts.

Figure 6.24: Map of comparison of AOD share percentage attributed to urban/industrial by the method using only 2 parameters (EAE and SSA) and all 5 parameters. The graph shows all selected AERONET stations and a histogram of all differences. The histogram shows mostly small differences, but the few larger differences appear in islands and coastal areas.

6.5.4 Comparison with CAMS: Maritime aerosols

Here we show the comparison between CAMS reanalysis and AERONET aerosols classifications for maritime aerosols.

Figure 6.25: Map of maritime aerosols comparisons between our classifications and the ones derived from CAMS reanalysis in the selected AERONET stations. We show the difference between the percentage of AOD, which we attributed to maritime aerosols minus the percentage of sea salt optical depth to the overall AOD in CAMS.

6.5.5 Additional station for the Amazon area

Cuiaba-Miranda, Brazil is at 210 m, -15.7N, -56.1E. Cuiaba is a city in Western Brazil with a population of nearly around 700000. The region is largely agricultural and close to the Amazon region, 500 km in straight line from Alta Floresta. The %AOD per type climatology showed similar patterns with Alta Floresta (urban/industrial and mixed aerosols, biomass burning seasonality) (Figure 6.25). The large decrease of AOD in September observed in Alta Floresta is visible here as well.

Figure 6.26: Panel a: Climatology of AOD and share of AOD attributed to each type or sub-type to the total AOD at 440 nm (coincident to the inversions). Panel b: The change of AOD and AOD share per month for each type or sub-type between the period ending in 2012 and the one starting at 2013.

List of abbreviations

AAE	Absorption Ångström Exponent
AAOD	Absorption Aerosol Optical Depth
AERONET	Aerosol Robotic Network
AOD	Aerosol Optical Depth
AOD _c	Coarse Mode Aerosol Optical Depth
AOD _f	Fine Mode Aerosol Optical Depth
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
EAE	Extinction Ångström Exponent
FMF	Fine mode fraction of AOD
GSFC	Goddard Space Flight Center
GWIS	Global Wildfire Information System
IRI	Imaginary part of the aerosol Refractive Index
MD	Mahalanobis Distance
RRI	Real part of the aerosol Refractive Index
SSA	Single Scattering Albedo
USA	United States of America

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